

DEVELOPMENT OF PLASMA TECHNOLOGY FOR CRACKING OIL RAW MATERIALS

A. Khakimov¹, Sh.T. Gulomov²

Technical Integrity Specialist, Technical Excellence Department at ADNOC Gas¹

Associate Professor of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology²

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Abstract. *The article contains information on the application of plasma technologies in oil refining processes, as well as on the possibilities of hydrogen synthesis in a cold and low-temperature plasma environment with subsequent utilization of hydrogen and particles based on highly reactive hydrogen in the technology of plasma cracking of heavy oil and residues.*

Keywords: *plazmacracking, plazma-chemical processes, plazmacracking reactions' mechanism.*

Introduction. It is known that plasma technology used in various industries is known as a new environmentally friendly technology. Some applications of plasma have been developed as industrial methods [1] and some others are being improved in the laboratory for use in various industries [1]. In a plasma environment, electrons, ions, and activated (active) radicals are able to collide with molecules, forming activated (active) particles, which play an important role in breaking chemical bonds. This ability of plasma can also be used to break C-C and C-H bonds and create new recombined hydrocarbons as process products [2]. In the oil industry, there are various methods of processing heavy and low-value raw materials into marketable products. In an oil refinery, light components are extracted from crude oil, and its heavy fractions, using secondary processing processes, are converted by chemical transformations into light hydrocarbons, which have a relatively higher flammability and, as a result, a higher market value. Cracking of petroleum hydrocarbons was originally carried out by thermal cracking, which has been almost completely replaced by catalytic cracking, since it produces more of the NK-180 fraction, a component of gasoline, which also has a higher octane number. Currently, the most commonly used process in oil refineries is Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) [3]–[5]. The by-product of the process is gases that are more olefinic and therefore more valuable than gases obtained by thermal cracking [3]–[5].

The feedstock for FCC is usually a fraction with an initial boiling point at atmospheric pressure of 340 °C or higher and an average molecular weight in the range from almost 200 to 600. This fraction of oil is also called heavy gas oil. The FCC process vaporizes and cracks long-chain molecules of high-boiling hydrocarbon liquids into molecules with much shorter chains by contacting the feedstock, at high temperature and moderate pressure, with a so-called fluidized powder catalyst [3]–[5]. In the FCC process, the powder catalyst has a high temperature and the reactor temperature is more than 510 °C. The process uses a reactor designed for the separation and regeneration of spent catalysts, which requires significant energy consumption and increases costs. Therefore, traditional hydrocarbon cracking technologies [5] need to take into account and solve problems associated with the time required to heat the catalyst, the availability of a hydrogen source, coke removal, etc. As an alternative technology, the use of non-thermal and/or low-

temperature plasma technology, which has become widespread in the field of chemistry and material processing, is proposed [6].

These technologies have a number of advantages over traditional cracking technologies, since the process does not require high excess pressure, and, as a result, capital-intensive equipment such as a hydrocracking reactor, separate hydrogen production units, process catalysts and related operations that are difficult to manufacture, transport, install and operate.

Active particles such as electrons, ions and excited radicals (ion-radicals) in a plasma environment can act as heat sources and a catalyst at the same time. These particles collide with molecules, providing the energy needed to break bonds. It is well known that cold plasma has low energy consumption and easily shifts thermodynamic equilibrium, due to which the desired chemical selectivity of reactions is achieved [6]. The chemistry of processes in such systems is determined precisely by the high energy of electrons, which also helps to achieve the desired chemical selectivity of the process.

Methodology. There are various types of non-thermal and low-temperature plasma reactors known, developed for use in various purposes. One of the simplest, inexpensive and frequently used reactors is shown in Fig. 1 dielectric barrier discharge reactor (DBDR) [6]–[8]. This type of reactor is capable of generating plasma at atmospheric pressure and ambient temperature, which may be an advantage for industrial applications compared to traditional reactors used in thermocatalytic processes.

Figure 1 - Dielectric barrier discharge reactor (DBDR).

DBDRs are characterized by the presence of one or more insulating layers in the current path between the metal electrodes in addition to the discharge gap [8]. Applying high voltage between two electrodes creates an ionized space with electrons with high initial energy, both internal (degree of ionization) and external (kinetic) energy. When hydrocarbons are fed into a reactor with ionized matter, excited electrons collide with hydrocarbon molecules, and if the collision of these particles has sufficient energy, the C–C and C–H bonds are broken. Collisions of electrons and ions with heavy hydrocarbons form activated radicals, which in turn recombine and lead to the production of hydrocarbons with shorter chains - the desired products of the process [9].

A number of published studies also show that hydrocarbon molecules C1–C9 are successfully cracked by various types of non-thermal plasma reactors [9]–[19]. In addition, such reactions can lead to the formation of hydrocarbons and oxygen-containing compounds heavier than the raw material, this occurs due to the combination of radicals in cold plasma reactors [9]–[19].

For example, in the article [20], an experimental setup was described to study the possibility and prove the ability of cold plasma to split heavy hydrocarbons (n-hexadecane, lubricating oil and heavy oil) into lighter hydrocarbons.

In plasma reactors, the main source of activation energy for chemical reactions is determined by the value of the power consumed for plasma production. Thus, the electrical characteristics of the reactor and the power consumed by it have a direct relationship with the activation energy of the ionized medium. In most scientific papers devoted to the study of the dependence of plasma properties on energy consumption, the Lissajous method is used [8], [21].

Results and discussion. The works [22], [23] show the scheme and the results of the operation of the plasma cracking unit using low-temperature plasma, which differs in temperature characteristics and the mechanism of action from cold plasma, namely, the plasma supply in the form of a jet, which increases both the initial energy of ionized particles and the temperature in the reaction zone, which in turn reduces the time of plasma action on the raw material and increases the selectivity of the process for target products. An important difference of the experiments is that the experiments were carried out on an industrial unit in which the flows of raw materials for the plasma processing already had an initial velocity and high initial energy (temperature up to 350 °C), as well as a small excess pressure. During the experiments, it was possible to empirically identify the dependences of the fractional composition of the process products on the feed rate, the initial temperature of the raw material and other process parameters.

process feedstock

product obtained at feed temperature of 200 °C

product obtained at feed temperature of 300 °C

Figure 2 - superposition of chromatograms of raw materials and products of the plasma-chemical treatment process.

The dependence of the composition of the process products on the initial temperature of the raw material supplied to the reactor is shown in Fig. 2, which is an overlay of the results of a chromatographic study of the raw material and the products of the plasma cracking process.

The dependence of the fractional composition of the products of plasma-chemical treatment on the feed rate of raw materials into the reactor is graphically shown in Fig. 3.

Proportion of distillate, %

Temperature, °C

Feed rate of feedstock

Figure 3 - Dependence of the composition of the product on the feed rate of the raw material into the reactor.

Experimentally, it was possible to find out that in the case of too low a flow rate, the raw material often passes the stage of the target highly profitable product - a component of liquid motor fuel (gasoline, kerosene, diesel fuel), decomposing to hydrocarbon gases. In the case of a high flow rate through the above-described reactor, the degree of conversion of the raw material decreases sharply.

As mentioned above, electrons play a key role in plasma processes. Since plasma affects not only the liquid but also the gas phase, electrons will participate in most reactions. The nature and mechanism of interaction of hydrocarbons in a plasma environment have not been fully studied; it is difficult to describe the role of electrons in plasma-chemical processes. There are two possible mechanisms: cracking of hydrocarbons and activation of hydrocarbons (creation of more reactive particles). The first is based on electron-mediated processes such as dissociation, dissociative ionization, vibrational excitation, and electron excitation of the parent hydrocarbon molecule, resulting in the formation of parent hydrocarbon fragments, radicals, or excited state particles (ions, ion-radicals). The second mechanism is ion-molecular reactions, in which ions

created by electron collisions (bombardment) react with neutral gas particles and produce particles that can stimulate reactions [24]–[27].

where x, y, m and n are integers and M denotes a neutral molecule.

As a result of ion recombination and/or charge transfer reaction following dissociative ionization, smaller, highly flammable molecular fragments are formed.

The authors of this article see the possibility of using methane as a plasma-forming gas or introducing methane into a plasma stream of another ionized gas for the purpose of its subsequent plasmolysis and enrichment with hydrogen, its radicals and ion radicals of the primary contact zones, reaction and quenching of the raw material of the plasma cracking process of heavy oil residues of primary oil distillation as a further development of plasma cracking technology and a promising direction of research.

The works [28], [25] describe methods for producing hydrogen by plasma cracking. For example, the work [28] describes the process of pyrolysis (plasmolysis) of methane using a high-frequency induction plasmatron of atmospheric pressure, similar in design and method of ionization of the plasma-forming gas to the technology of plasma cracking of heavy oil residues studied by the authors [22], [23].

The studied dependences of the degree of conversion of methane and the rate of hydrogen production on the process conditions demonstrated that the degree of conversion of methane into hydrogen can reach values close to 100% [28]. The scheme of the technical solution is presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Methane pyrolysis plant diagram.

Conclusion. The formed hydrogen, as well as ions and ion-radicals of the hydrogen atom will promote hydrogenation reactions directly in the zone of the main reactions in close proximity to the area of plasma action on the raw material, the excess of reactive particles in the zone of secondary reactions - the hardening zone, will also increase the yield of hydrocarbons with shorter chains filling the open valence bonds formed after the decay of the initial molecules with a high molecular weight, reducing the number of recombination reactions with the formation of

compounds with double and triple bonds. Also, by regulating the methane supply, it is possible to obtain the desired selectivity of the process for the final products.

The formed ions, ion-radicals of carbon will also participate in the plasma cracking process as reactive particles. This change in the process technology will lead to a decrease in the supply of water vapor or its complete replacement with methane as a plasma-forming gas, which will lead to a decrease in the amount of oxygen-containing compounds in the reaction product, the formation and deposition of soot in the products and on the internal walls of the installation equipment.

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